
LACK OF INFRASTRUCTURE, PROPER CARE OF GOVERNMENT AND OVERLOAD OF POPULATION IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS GIVE BIRTH TO PRIVATE CLINICS: A CASE STUDY BESIDES THE DISTRICT HOSPITAL (JANGLATMANDI) ANANTNAG, JAMMU AND KASHMIR, INDIA

Towseef Mohi Ud Din, Tariq Ahmad Bhat, Lateef Ahmad Mir

Ph.D. Research Scholars, Department of school of studies in economics
Vikram University Ujjain, (M.P) India.

ABSTRACT

This article reviews the working of private health care clinics besides the district public hospital (Anantnag), and emphasizes the role that they can play in providing the health care services. The aim of this paper is that, how lack of infrastructure, proper care of government and overload of population in public hospitals become burden in utilizing the health care services. It has been observed that the demand for the private health care got valid reasons as mentioned above. The comprehensive idea of all respondents depicts a picture that the public health care centers want proper attention like to increase the staff and employ qualified and experienced doctors by which common people get full benefit from government health care services by which people get rid from exploitation which they experience in those private clinics.

KEY WORDS: Health Care, Private Clinics, Public Hospital, Services, Utilization.

INTRODUCTION

The public healthcare system of India has grown leap bound but policy formulation on the basis of public healthcare data is still not being carried out. Health Planners and management personnel rely mainly on the basis of previous experiences to formulate ad hoc decisions rather than seeking relevant data^[1]. The levels of distribution of health care facilities in any region manifest itself at the level of health and human well-being. The spatial distribution of health care facilities appears to be affected by interrelated factors of physiographic constraints, socioeconomic and various demographic characteristics^[2]. The scheme of Integrated Child Development Service is the foremost symbol of India's commitment to her children. India's response to the challenge of providing preschool education on one hand and breaking the vicious cycle of malnutrition, morbidity, reduced learning capacity and morbidity, on the other. Despite of the fact that huge allocations have been made by the Central Government for ICDS in Jammu and Kashmir, the development in basic infrastructure and improvements in amenities/facilities has been inadequate, especially in rural areas of the state^[3]. Awareness campaigns are often used to encourage medical screening that allows for early detection of health problems, but much remains unknown about the effectiveness of these programs^[4]. The alarming numbers of preventable maternal, newborn and child deaths that still occur each year are indicative of the significant challenge the world face to save the lives of the most vulnerable women and their young children^[5].

AN OVER VIEW ON PRIVATIZATION OF HEALTH CARE

To improve the health care services and provide the easy medication against the illness of the people the government take many remarkable steps for the well-being of the people from last 30 years. Under the eight plan human development was adopted as ultimate aim, for which many measures have been taken such as to reduce infant mortality rate and maternal mortality rate, such as reproductive and child health care scheme, integrated child development scheme, child survival and safe motherhood scheme (lunched in 1992-93) and mid-day meal scheme etc., and private health care benefits and remunerations are given under the fringe benefits. At the same passage of time the state government of Jammu and Kashmir take one of the remarkable step which is that they rebuilt the district hospital Anantnag with strength of 110 beds, 7 theatres, 10 OPD rooms and advanced equipment's has been employed. Apart from this, district hospital lack "specialist as a result of which the doctors are forced to refer the patients to Shri Maharaja Hari Singh Hospital Srinagar (SMHS) hospital and Sher-I-Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences Srinagar (SKIMS) Soura. Despite being a referral hospital there is no specialist either in medicine, ENT, Ophthalmology or Orthopedic. The junior doctors and Assistant Surgeons with only MBBS degrees maintain the casualties and they are forced to refer the patients to SMHS and SKIMS for treatment" ^[6], which give birth to the private health care centers.

METHODS

Research design, analysis and different supporting tools for this study have been taken purposively with over-all background in health care services.

Data Source: Comprehensive information on privet health care services (utilization, quality, expenditures) has been conceder during the year 2017. Observation and interview method for manipulating the variables has been employed for getting the gross root level knowledge about the utilization of private health care services.

Sample: The analytical study has been done on 50 private health care centers with in the area of district hospital Anantnag.

Measures Dependent Variables: Four variables have been used to examine health care services. The categories were privet health care centers, government interference, infrastructure and population. Where privet health care centers are dependent variable and rest may independent variables.

Statistical Analysis: The regression and demand function models are used to show the dependence of different variables on each other.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the current status of district hospital Anantnag
- To study the working of private health care clinics in district Anantnag.

RESULTS

Health care is necessity good weather an income of a person increases or decrease he is utilizing the private healthcare services because when a person cannot get proper services in government health care centers that time he finds a need to utilized the private health care services. The first part of the results shows that private health centers earn fame because they provide good services as compare to public health care centers. As we see when a disease was cured properly in privet clinics the utilization and expenditure on private health care increased passively as shown in figure 1.1, so we can say that utilization is the function of cure. On the other hand, the utilization of private health care services can be shown mathematically as under:

$$C = f(X_1, X_2)$$

C= cure, X_1 = utilization of private health care services, X_2 = expenditure on private health care services. In the above model it has been shown that there is a direct relationship between the cure and the utilization of the private health care services. An individual spend without worrying on the private health service when he got proper treatment of illness because he knows that health is wealth. In today’s world health service is considered as a consumer good which an individual can demand on different stages of life, which is influenced by many variables like other consumer goods as shown in blow equation.

$$Q = b_0 + b_1p + b_2 I + b_3Y.$$

Q = quantity demanded of private health care services

P = average fee (price) in private health clinics

I= infrastructure in public health care centers

Y = income of patient

b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 = coefficients of demand equation for private health services

Now in second part of the results, 50 private health care clinics have been visited in the month of September 2017 in which four Sundays has employed as sample for study because mostly these clinics are open only on that day. Due to holiday it has been observed that large number of patient visit on that day, because the working class of the society got only that day for utilizing the health care services. And another factors responsible for that the private centers provide good services as compare to public health care centers, over population and absence of proper government care are another factor by which these private clinics get full-fledged.

On an average 20 – 60 patients visit these private clinics on every Sunday. Because public health cares’s centers cannot provide the satisfactory services to the public, which is observed during the survey.

Table 1.1: over all view of private health care clinics in district Anantnag beside public hospital

Private clinics around district public hospital Anantnag	Fee for every visit by patients	Price of medicine after every visit, recommended by physician*	No. of Patients visit on every Sunday
1 st	300	1050	33
2 nd	600	500	56
3 rd	400	420	40
4 th	500	700	20
5 th	500	300	44
6 th	200	400	54
7 th	300	800	44
8 th	600	200	34
9 th	500	400	35
10 th	400	500	32
11 th	400	500	45
12 th	400	330	55
13 th	400	600	50
14 th	600	730	50
15 th	500	540	51
16 th	500	970	37
17 th	500	230	45
18 th	300	150	22
19 th	400	250	58
20 th	500	200	47
21 th	500	440	50
22 th	500	550	60
23 th	400	760	45
24 th	400	300	45
25 th	400	290	41
26 th	500	180	23
27 th	500	400	21
28 th	500	300	33
29 th	500	850	54
30 th	500	770	43
31 th	300	443	60
32 th	200	500	60
33 th	300	540	28
34 th	500	600	30
35 th	500	760	25
36 th	300	435	25
37 th	300	765	54
38 th	300	500	39
39 th	300	510	48
40 th	300	570	37
41 th	400	768	56
42 th	300	433	40
43 th	400	635	27
44 th	400	844	60
45 th	400	237	34

46 th	300	955	26
47 th	500	790	40
48 th	500	456	40
49 th	300	550	51
50 th	400	400	26

Source: primary survey

* Total number of 5 patients has been interviewed from each private health care clinic

Fig. 1.2

Source: primary survey

The above table 1.1 shows that the average fee paid by every patient is 414 Rs and average expenditure on medicines after every visit is 526.02 Rs, at the same time it has been proved that 41.46 patients visit every Sunday in these private clinics besides the districts public hospital Anantnag.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Anantnag district is mainly inhabited by Kashmiris who constitute 89.25% of the population. The Kandi (untrodden areas) of the district are inhabited by Gujjar’s and Bakerwals and are 10.75% of the district population. The measure population of district Anantnag still lacks the medical facilities. The government should take measure steps to provide the health services to door steps for each individual and also raise the good staff and quality infrastructure in public health care centers, by which the common people should not, exploited by the private health clinics. Recently India government passed the GST bill in which the tax slab on healthcare has been reduced from 5% to 0%, but this is not an end a lot has been still to be done.

CONCLUSION

It is an old saying that, “need is the mother of invention” as we see that the public health care center of district Anantnag lack many facilities by which these private health care clinics come into existence and exploited the common masses. No doubt they provide good services but for poor or middle class families it become burden to utilized these services because they are so expansive for them as we see in the above table 1.1 (expenditure on medicine and fee). If there is proper care of government on public health care center (Janglatmandi) Anantnag the common masses cannot exploit by these private clinics.

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